

Electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of TPE composites containing carbon fillers

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Abstract

Ethylene-octene copolymer (EOC) is a copolymer which exhibits low density, good elasticity and improved processability and widely being used in the automotive, electrical cable insulation and footwear applications. Conducting polymer composites of EOC were prepared using three different types of fillers; expandable graphite (EG), multiwall carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and carbon fiber (CF). Electrical (both AC and DC) and thermal conductivities of composites were measured. Flammability resistance tests of the EOC/EG composites only were carried out and showed that expandable graphite is an excellent flame-retardant filler. Percolation behaviour of EOC/EG composites were observed at around 16 vol. % of filler loading while for EOC/CF it was at, 2.21 vol. % and for EOC/MWCNT, it was at 5.32 vol.% which is a clear indication of effect of filler, or aspect ratio of fillers in the composites. From shore-A hardness values, it is clear that even the highest filler level did not reduce the softness of composites. Good electrical/thermal conductivities and improved mechanical properties along with comparable shore-A hardness values of EOC composites with excellent residual strain (ϵ_r) of pure EOC which is a direct measure of elasticity of a material, shows the potential of EOC to find its application as strain sensor.

Materials and methods

EOC used was Dow's ethylene-octene copolymer (octene content of 45 wt. %). EOC/EG composites were prepared by melt blending of EOC and EG, while EOC/MWCNT and EOC/CF composites were prepared by ultrasonication of EOC solutions/filler systems followed by precipitation. DC conductivity was measured using Van der Pauw four-point method and AC conductivity by Agilent RF Impedance Analyser and Hioky 3522 LCR Hi Tester. Thermal conductivity measurement was carried out by Fitch method. Tensile and thermal properties were analyzed by standard methods. Morphology of composites were studied by Vega II LMU Tescan SEM with a beam acceleration voltage set at 10 kV.

Results

Conclusions

EOC composites of carbon fillers show improvement in thermal and electrical conductivities and mechanical properties without compromising in their hardness values proving their potential to be used as candidates for pressure/strain sensors.

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